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Responsible Author(s): Valerie Brown (RCN); Leon Kapetas (RCN);
Contributions from: Shuntian Wang (ETH), Christie Walker (ETH)
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BIOTRAILS Partners	
<p>CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE Piazzale aldo Moro 7, 00185 Roma, Italy</p>	
<p>CHAROKOPEIO PANEPISTIMIO Eleftheriou Venizelou 70, 176 71 Athens, Greece</p>	
<p>ADELPHI RESEARCH GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH Alt-Moabit 91, 10559 Berlin, Germany</p>	
<p>WHITE RESEARCH SPRL Avenue de la Toison D'Or 67, 1060 Saint Gilles, Belgium</p>	
<p>STICHTING GLOBAL RESILIENT CITIES NETWORK Korte Hoogstraat 31, 3011 Rotterdam, Netherlands</p>	
<p>DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL SA Themistokli Sofouli Str. 54-56, 54655 Thessaloniki, Greece</p>	
<p>EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED Arch. Makariou III & Mesaorias 1 Office 101, 2322 Nicosia, Cyprus</p>	
<p>CENTRO INTERNACIONAL DE AGRICULTURA TROPICAL Kilometro 17 Recta Cali, 763537 Palmira, Colombia</p>	
<p>HELLENIC AQUACULTURE PRODUCERS ORGANIZATION Leoforos Lavriou 99B, 19002 Paiania, Greece</p>	
<p>KWAME NKUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY KUMASI Private Mail Bag, University Post Office, Kumasi Ash, Ghana</p>	
<p>EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH Rämistr. 101, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland</p>	

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
CBI	City Biodiversity Index – also known as the Singapore Index, a self-assessment tool for cities to evaluate their biodiversity conservation efforts.
CLCplus	CORINE Land Cover Plus – a high-resolution land cover product from Copernicus used to assess urban green space and land use changes.

Copernicus	The EU's Earth observation programme providing satellite and in-situ data for environmental monitoring, including biodiversity and land use.
EEMRIO	Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output – a modelling technique that traces environmental pressures (e.g., land use, emissions) across global supply chains.
EIA / ESIA	Environmental Impact Assessment / Environmental and Social Impact Assessment – formal processes to evaluate the environmental and social effects of proposed projects.
LAU	Local Administrative Unit – a territorial division used for statistical and governance purposes, such as municipalities or communes in Europe.
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging – a remote sensing method that uses laser light to map surfaces, including urban tree cover.
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation – a non-profit, voluntary citizens' group that is independent from government, often active in environmental, social, and policy issues.
NRR	Nature Restoration Regulation – a 2024 EU regulation requiring Member States to halt the decline of biodiversity and restore ecosystems, including in urban areas.
Ramsar Site	A wetland site designated to be of international importance under the Ramsar Convention, which focuses on the conservation of wetlands.
Scope 1	Biodiversity impacts within a city's administrative boundaries, often from direct urban activities such as construction, pollution, and green space management.
Scope 2	Biodiversity impacts in peri-urban and regional areas caused by infrastructure and services that support urban life (e.g., water supply, energy systems).
Scope 3	Global biodiversity impacts driven by urban consumption through supply chains, such as land use change for food production or raw material extraction.
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals – a set of 17 global goals adopted by the UN to promote sustainability, equity, and environmental protection.
Three-Scope Approach	A framework adapted from the GHG Protocol to assess biodiversity impacts at local (Scope 1), regional (Scope 2), and global (Scope 3) scales.
UNP	Urban Nature Plan – a strategic plan developed by a city to protect, enhance, and monitor urban nature and biodiversity

ABSTRACT

This technical publication summarises the methodological framework and applied findings from Deliverable 4.4 of the BIOTRAILS project. It presents the rationale for bridging knowledge and action in urban biodiversity, introduces the three-scope framework, and outlines approaches for quantifying biodiversity impacts across local, regional, and global scales. Case studies, including Bristol's biodiversity net gain regulation, Athens' water supply system, and global supply chain assessments, illustrate application of the framework. The discussion highlights how city initiatives align with the framework, the implications for policy and planning, and concludes with recommendations for cities to act as biodiversity stewards.

1 INTRODUCTION

While global biodiversity trends remain deeply concerning [1], this deliverable shifts attention from global statistics to practical, localised strategies. The three-scope framework is intentionally designed to accommodate the varied ecological, governance, and data realities of different cities. Whether a city is just beginning to address biodiversity or already has advanced planning in place, the framework offers a flexible tool to prioritise actions, identify gaps, and support cross-sector collaboration. For instance, a small municipality might focus on Scope 1 using available green space data, while a larger city could target Scope 3 through sustainable procurement. The framework is structured to be user-friendly for both technical staff and decision-makers, helping translate high-level sustainability goals into specific, actionable interventions. Its indicators, case examples, and quantification methods can inform updates to existing climate, procurement, or nature plans—empowering cities to tailor biodiversity action to their own context.

2 A FRAMEWORK FOR INTEGRATED BIODIVERSITY IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The three-scope framework provides a structured lens through which cities can identify and address their biodiversity impacts at different spatial scales. Adapted from the well-established GHG Protocol [2], this model helps urban stakeholders distinguish between direct, indirect, and supply-chain-related pressures on ecosystems. Figure 1 graphically presents how the three scopes could be adapted in the context of biodiversity. The three-scope approach can be easily understood at a conceptual level. However, its practical implementation requires producing solid quantitative evidence using a combination of techniques varying from earth observation, biodiversity analysis, regional trade analytics as well as harmonisation and integration of data across spatial and temporal scales when/where these are available. Besides, the recognised scientific challenges in quantifying biodiversity and its change over time will apply also in the proposed framework [3].

Scope 1

Scope 2

Scope 3

Biodiversity within city boundaries

Biodiversity nearby that supports city systems

Biodiversity far away that is connected to city activities.

Figure 1: The three-scopes described in brief. Source: Designed in Canva 2024

While simple in concept, applying the framework in practice requires cities to assess diverse data types, governance levers, and ecological risks across each scope.

Scope 1 – Biodiversity within the city:

Scope 1 captures biodiversity impacts occurring within a city’s administrative boundaries, often resulting from urbanisation, land-use change, pollution, and local infrastructure development. These impacts are the most visible and commonly targeted by city policies. For instance, habitat fragmentation due to road construction, the spread of invasive alien species, and the loss of green space can all reduce species richness and ecosystem health within city limits [4], [5]. Cities can mitigate these impacts through urban greening programs, nature-based solutions, and land-use planning that protects critical habitats. Indicators such as tree canopy cover, number of native species, and green space per capita are often used to track progress. Tools like the City Biodiversity Index (CBI), also known as the Singapore Index [6], provide cities with a self-assessment framework to benchmark their performance. From a policy perspective, Scope 1 impacts are often easiest to act upon because they are within the city’s jurisdiction and involve local data and infrastructure.

Scope 2 – Regional infrastructure and services:

Scope 2 addresses biodiversity impacts that occur beyond city boundaries but are driven by the infrastructure and services that support urban life. This includes energy systems, water supply, wastewater treatment, and waste management facilities that may be situated in peri-urban or regional landscapes. These systems often require substantial land conversion, disrupt habitats, or alter hydrological regimes—for example, through the construction of reservoirs, pipelines, and transmission corridors [7]. While cities may not directly operate these facilities, they influence them through procurement choices, land-use regulation, and partnerships with utilities. Cities often lack adequate data to track Scope 2 impacts and rarely consider them in biodiversity plans. However, environmental and social impact assessments (ESIAs), when designed with biodiversity-specific indicators [8], can help evaluate risks and identify mitigation opportunities. Recent examples such as the Billion Oyster Project in New York and the Green Wedges strategy in Melbourne illustrate how cities can work with external actors to enhance biodiversity outcomes in regional systems.

Scope 3 – Global supply chains and consumption:

Scope 3 encompasses biodiversity pressures linked to the production and transport of goods and services consumed by urban residents but produced elsewhere—often across national or continental distances. These include impacts from deforestation, overfishing, mining, and water depletion associated with imported food, textiles, timber, and electronics [4], [5]. Because Scope 3 impacts are diffuse, cities often overlook them in planning frameworks. However, evidence suggests these impacts can significantly outweigh those in Scope 1 and 2 [9]. In this report, we pilot the use of Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) modelling to trace the land-use impacts of banana imports as a proxy for biodiversity loss. Bananas were selected for this demonstration due to their robust data availability in the FABIO database. While challenging, Scope 3 offers a powerful opportunity for cities to lead in global sustainability through sustainable

procurement, awareness campaigns, and supply chain transparency initiatives. It also provides a point of leverage for embedding biodiversity into circular economy and climate neutrality agendas.

3 QUANTIFYING BIODIVERSITY IMPACTS

This chapter introduces methods for quantifying biodiversity impacts across the three scopes, with examples from cities and case studies. The goal is to move from a static framework to an adaptive tool informed by practice, enabling cities to measure and act on biodiversity impacts more effectively. Importantly, this is an early-stage, proof-of-concept approach to biodiversity impact quantification—intended not as a definitive assessment, but as a first step for cities to begin understanding their biodiversity footprints across scales. Measuring biodiversity loss is inherently complex due to its multidimensional nature, spatial variability, and the lack of comprehensive indicators. Nevertheless, even partial estimates can inform decision-making and drive more targeted urban biodiversity policies.

For Scope 1—direct impacts within city boundaries—the analysis focuses on land use change, habitat loss, and the extent of urban green space and tree canopy cover. These indicators are aligned with Article 8 of the EU Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), which mandates no net loss by 2030 and a progressive increase thereafter. Scope 2 examines the indirect biodiversity impacts arising from infrastructure and services that support urban life but extend beyond the city, such as water supply systems, energy infrastructure, and waste management. This is illustrated through a case study on Athens’ water network, highlighting the regional ecological consequences of large-scale water extraction and conveyance. Scope 3 addresses biodiversity impacts embedded in global supply chains, using a proof-of-concept Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) analysis of imports. This approach traces consumption-driven land use and biodiversity pressures from European cities to producing regions abroad, capturing the externalised nature of urban ecological footprints.

3.1 SCOPE 1

Urbanisation represents a significant driver of biodiversity loss, primarily through land-use change and habitat degradation. The expansion of built environments typically results in the fragmentation, alteration, or complete removal of natural habitats, thereby disrupting ecological processes and reducing habitat availability for a wide range of species. In addition to physical transformation, urban areas introduce multiple environmental stressors, including pollution, anthropogenic noise, artificial light, and the spread of invasive alien species, all of which contribute to declines in biodiversity at local and regional scales.

Despite these pressures, urban areas also present opportunities for biodiversity conservation and enhancement. The integration of green infrastructure—such as parks, green roofs, vegetated corridors, and urban wetlands—can support native species, improve ecological connectivity, and contribute to the provision of ecosystem services. When effectively planned and managed, urban ecosystems can provide important refugia for biodiversity and serve as critical components of broader ecological networks, particularly in densely populated regions.

In this context, the following section outlines the latest monitoring and quantification obligations for urban nature restoration as set forth in the EU Nature Restoration Regulation, adopted in August 2024 [10]. As the first EU regulation to set binding urban ecosystem targets, the NRR offers a timely and policy-relevant anchor for biodiversity impact assessment at the city scale. Specifically, Article 8 of the NRR focuses on urban ecosystems, setting ambitious targets for the *no net loss* of green

urban space and tree cover by 2030, and a *steady increase* in their total area from 2030 onwards. While limited to two specific targets, the spirit of the Regulation is to enhance biodiversity, habitat quality, and increase climate resilience across the European territory, in cities and beyond. Effective monitoring of progress is essential to ensure compliance and measure the impact of urban nature restoration efforts.

The entry point to understanding biodiversity impacts in the city is through assessing urban green space and tree canopy cover, as well as complementing with assessments in key thematic areas offering potential indicators to complement the targets set in Art. 8 of the NRR.

In brief, Article 8 of the NRR sets targets for urban ecosystems which Member States are required to meet. Specifically, it indicates the following targets:

1. Member States shall ensure that there is no net loss in the total national areas of urban green space and of urban tree canopy cover in urban ecosystem areas by 2030, compared to the situation in 2024.
2. Member States shall progressively increase the total national areas of urban green space as of 2031, with a 6-year revision period, until satisfactory level of greening is achieved. The increase is achieved through the integration of green spaces in buildings and infrastructure.
3. Member States shall achieve an increasing trend of urban tree canopy cover in each urban ecosystem area, measured every six years from 1 January 2031, until a satisfactory level is achieved.

Figure 2 illustrates the roadmap for implementation of Article 8 of the NRR by national and local governments.

Figure 2: Roadmap of implementation of Article 8 (Source: Anne Franklin, Brussels Institute of Statistics and Analysis, Perspective Brussels – [webinar series](#) Greening Cities Partnership)

To evaluate progress against these targets, Member States, through municipalities or local authorities will need to monitor indicators on urban green spaces and tree canopy cover. The following sections provide guidance on how this can be achieved using publicly available data, and make suggestions for complementary assessments.

3.1.1 Monitoring the Extent of Urban Green Spaces

Assessing urban green space coverage requires consistent data collection obtained through remote sensing and/or field surveys, and processing in Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Tracking changes over time helps urban areas measure compliance with no net loss targets and identify areas for restoration.

The assessment can be carried out using the CLCplus Backbone powered by Copernicus' Land Monitoring Service [11]. The product constitutes the baseline land cover product for Europe providing comprehensive, seamless, and accurate land cover information for multiple domains and applications such as environmental monitoring, land use planning, climate change-related assessments and emergency management. It has a raster format and a resolution of 10 meters, showing the dominant land cover among 11 basic land-cover classes. Urban green space is considered the total area covered by trees, bushes, shrubs, permanent herbaceous vegetation, lichens and mosses, ponds and watercourses found within cities or towns and suburbs. Figure 3 shows land cover for the city of Padova: aggregating the abovementioned cover types results in the total urban green space area. Changes can be detected and measured between years in a GIS application.

Figure 3: Land cover for the city of Padova, Italy. In green boxes in the legend those cover types contributing to urban green spaces (Source: Produced by Gracia Zulian, consultant, JRC – [webinar series](#) Greening Cities Partnership)

3.1.2 Monitoring Urban Tree Canopy Cover

The [Copernicus Land Monitoring Service](#) also provides the High Resolution Layer Tree Cover Density product which offers information on the percentage of tree cover in a given area [11]. With its three-year update cycle and high-resolution data, this product is one of best publicly available European tree cover maps. The product has a 10 meters resolution.

Figure 4: Tree density cover for the city of Padova, Italy (Source: Produced by Gracia Zulian, consultant, JRC – [webinar series](#) Greening Cities Partnership)

While the Copernicus openly available products provide a satisfactory resolution for the monitoring and evaluation of the proposed NRR targets, local surveys (e.g. of passive high resolution optical imagery and/or active airborne LiDAR remote sensing [12] or other data platforms can often provide a better resolution. By extension, results may differ between the two analyses. This is the case for the Metropolitan Region of Brussels particularly for low tree cover density areas which are better detected by a locally carried survey (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Brussel tree cover density using Copernicus data (left) and using local aerial survey data (right). Source: Produced by Anne Franklin, Brussels Institute of Statistics and Analysis, [Perspective Brussels – webinar series](#) Greening Cities Partnership

3.1.3 Spatial scales for monitoring and evaluation

The choice of the reference urban ecosystem area will have implications on the outcomes of the assessment. Member States are able to choose whether the assessment is performed at the Local Administrative Unit (LAU) level or in aggregated spatial extents represented by City Centres or City Clusters. In the latter case, it is evident that averaging takes place over a larger area. Such clusters

are based on grid-based analysis at 1000 meter resolution, considering each cell's population density. More information can be found in this interactive resource (see Figure 6) [13].

Figure 6: Definition of urban centres and towns based on grid density analysis (Source: DG Regional and Urban Policy)

Moreover, as shown in Figure 2, exemptions apply for LAUs or City Centres where the urban green space or the urban tree canopy cover exceed 45% and 10% of the total area respectively.

3.1.4 Complementary Indicators for Urban Nature Plans

The Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) encourages the restoration of urban ecosystems, with a focus on increasing green spaces and tree canopy. However, it does not require cities to develop Urban Nature Plans (UNPs) nor does it offer a complete set of indicators for urban biodiversity. Instead, it supports the broader aims of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which calls on cities with over 20,000 inhabitants to develop and implement such plans. Within this broader framework, complementary indicators can help cities measure progress in both the quantity and quality of nature in urban areas.

One useful reference is the work of the Greening Cities Partnership under the Urban Agenda for the EU. Their proposed indicators—adapted from the European Commission's handbook on evaluating Nature-based Solutions—provide a practical basis for cities to develop their own Urban Nature Plans. These indicators are especially relevant for quantifying Scope 1 biodiversity impacts: those that result directly from land-use change, green space management, and other municipal activities within the city's administrative boundaries. As such, they provide a foundational tool for cities aiming to track and report on their direct ecological impacts. A summary of these indicators is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Indicative complementary indicators for Urban Nature Plans (Source: GCP)

Theme	Potential complementary indicators
Green Space Management	Share of public and private green urban areas

Biodiversity enhancement	Number and type of trees and shrubs planted Control of invasive species in flora and fauna
Ecological connectivity	Urban tree canopy cover (linked to the mandatory indicators) Number of connected green spaces with ecological function
Climate Resilience	Species of the municipal inventory of trees and shrubs adapted to future climate
Environmental co-benefits	Air Quality Improvement potential (including conventional pollutants and/or PAHs)
Social co-benefits	Proximity to green spaces Accessibility to green spaces
Economic co-benefits and jobs creation	Economic value of urban nature
Participatory planning and governance	Degree of stakeholder and citizen engagement, e.g. through Citizen Assemblies, Local Green Council or similar.

3.1.5 Implications for Cities

To meet the targets outlined in Article 8 of the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), strong coordination is needed between national governments—responsible for drafting National Restoration Plans—and local authorities, who are at the frontline of implementation. Policy coherence across governance levels will be essential to ensure that urban renaturing efforts align with broader planning, climate, and land-use priorities.

Delivering on these ambitions will require not only technical support and dedicated financing but also local capacity to identify and act on opportunities for direct intervention. Cities play a key role in restoring biodiversity through land management, park maintenance, street tree planting, and control of invasive species—all of which fall under Scope 1. Quantifying these direct impacts helps cities prioritise high-leverage actions and demonstrate progress toward restoration goals.

Engaging the broader urban ecosystem—including businesses, landowners, and community organisations—will also be vital to scaling nature restoration. Shared ownership and capacity-building across sectors can unlock innovative partnerships and ensure that renaturing efforts are inclusive and locally relevant. Finally, cultivating public support through awareness-raising and encouraging pro-nature behaviours among residents will be crucial to sustaining long-term transformation.

3.1.6 Bristol Case Study

The Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) regulation implemented by Bristol City Council represents a state-of-the-art approach to embedding biodiversity outcomes within the urban planning system. Mandated by the UK's Environment Act (2021), BNG requires that all new developments deliver at least a 10% net gain in biodiversity relative to their pre-development state, and that this gain be maintained for a minimum of 30 years. What makes Bristol's implementation exemplary is the combination of legal enforceability, standardized measurement tools, and integration into the planning process from project inception to post-construction monitoring.

Bristol's approach is grounded in a statutory biodiversity metric that quantifies habitat value based on key variables such as distinctiveness, condition, size, and strategic significance. This metric is applied both before and after development to calculate biodiversity unit changes, ensuring that gains are demonstrable and auditable. A detailed guidance framework sets out rules, hierarchies,

and principles, while mechanisms like conservation covenants and Section 106 agreements ensure long-term legal enforcement.

Crucially, the BNG framework is not just a reporting tool but a driver of design. It embeds ecological thinking into spatial planning through a multidisciplinary lens, incentivizing developers to retain and enhance habitats on-site, or where necessary, to invest in legally secured off-site compensation. This proactive, quantified, and enforceable model positions Bristol as a leader in aligning development with ecological regeneration. It exemplifies how cities can move from aspirational greening policies to binding regulations that genuinely reverse biodiversity loss. As such, it serves as a critical reference for cities across Europe seeking to align with the Nature Restoration Regulation and operationalize Scope 1 biodiversity assessments within urban boundaries.

3.2 SCOPE 2

Urban areas depend on extensive infrastructure systems and service networks that often extend well beyond their administrative boundaries. Key sectors such as water supply and wastewater treatment, waste management, and energy provision require large-scale installations, resource extraction, and land-use modifications across peri-urban and regional landscapes. These systems, while essential for sustaining urban populations, can have significant and often overlooked impacts on biodiversity. For example, the construction of reservoirs, pipelines, energy corridors, and landfill sites may lead to habitat loss, ecosystem fragmentation, and altered hydrological regimes, thereby affecting both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems in surrounding regions.

These types of impacts fall under Scope 2: they are not caused directly by the city's own land-use change, but are the result of goods and services consumed by the urban population and institutions. Quantifying Scope 2 pressures is critical for understanding the broader ecological footprint of cities and identifying leverage points for more sustainable procurement, planning, and infrastructure decision-making.

Given the strong context dependency of infrastructure design and environmental conditions, it is critical to consider local and regional specificities when assessing potential biodiversity impacts. In this regard, the following section introduces a case study focusing on the water supply system for the Athens metropolitan area. This example serves to illustrate how infrastructure serving urban populations can influence biodiversity outcomes across broader geographic scales.

3.2.1 The expansion of Athens' water supply system

The metropolitan region of Athens, accounting for a substantial proportion of Greece's population, has historically faced considerable challenges in securing reliable water resources [14]. Initially reliant on nearby sources—most notably the Marathon Reservoir, completed in 1931—Athens' water supply infrastructure has undergone successive expansions in response to increasing urban water demand and the intensification of hydrological droughts, particularly during the prolonged drought of the late 1980s and early 1990s. Over time, additional sources were integrated into the system, including Lake Yliki in 1959, the Mornos Reservoir in 1980, and the Evinos Reservoir in 2001. These augmentations have progressively extended the city's dependence on remote catchments, with some located over 200 kilometres from the urban core, thereby embedding Athens' water security within a broader regional hydrological context.

Figure 7: Water sources for the city of Athens, Source: Sargentis, 2019

3.2.2 Regional hydroecological impacts

This reliance on distant surface water resources has necessitated the interception and regulation of multiple river systems, most notably the Mornos and Evinos rivers. The construction of large-scale reservoirs and conveyance infrastructure has significantly altered the natural hydrological regimes of these catchments. Impoundment has resulted in the permanent flooding of upstream areas, entailing the transformation or loss of terrestrial habitats. Downstream, altered flow regimes have led to a reduction in freshwater availability for riparian and aquatic ecosystems. In recognition of these impacts, environmental flow requirements have been incorporated into water management strategies; for example, a regulated minimum flow of $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ is maintained downstream of the Evinos Dam to support ecological functions and ecosystem services [15]. The deltaic wetland and the life it supports is nonetheless impacted.

Hydrological regulation has also disrupted sediment transport processes, contributing to increased erosion in downstream and coastal areas due to sediment retention within reservoirs. The Evinos river delta has retreated 350 meters over the last 71 years, partly due to reduced sediment deposition after the construction of the dam upstream [16]. Furthermore, reduced infiltration and recharge rates have been associated with declining groundwater levels, heightening the risk of saltwater intrusion in vulnerable coastal aquifers. At the same time, the newly formed reservoirs have given rise to novel aquatic habitats, some of which are subject to strict environmental protection measures. The Evinos Reservoir, in particular, forms part of the Messolonghi–Aitoliko Lagoons complex, which is designated under the Ramsar Convention as a wetland of international importance. These protective designations have imposed significant constraints on upstream land uses, limiting agricultural and industrial activity and thereby contributing to the conservation of regional biodiversity. For instance, regular monitoring of the water sources demonstrates consistently high water quality, as reflected in both physicochemical and biological indicators [14].

3.2.3 Implications for decision making and environmental management

The pronounced demographic and economic disparity between the Athens metropolitan region and its water-supplying catchments provides a strong rationale for the development of inter-basin infrastructure. Given the concentration of population, industrial activity, and service demand in the capital, the strategic allocation of water resources from comparatively low-density, rural upstream regions can be viewed as a rational response to regional resource imbalances. However, this case also exemplifies Scope 2 biodiversity impacts—those arising from infrastructure and services located outside urban boundaries but essential to sustaining urban life. The ecological implications of such interventions necessitate robust regulatory safeguards. In this regard, the systematic application of Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), alongside the formulation and implementation of evidence-based environmental management plans, is essential. These mechanisms serve to identify, monitor, and mitigate potential adverse effects on both pre-existing and newly created ecosystems, thereby supporting the ecological integrity of the affected landscapes and ensuring compliance with national and international conservation obligations.

3.3 SCOPE 3

While Scope 2 highlights the ecological consequences of infrastructure outside city boundaries, Scope 3 shifts the focus to impacts embedded in global consumption and supply chains. Quantifying biodiversity impacts linked to urban activities—what we define as Scope 3—is both essential and challenging. These impacts occur far beyond city boundaries, embedded in the complex, global supply chains that provide food, clothing, construction materials, and electronics to urban populations. While cities may not directly see or control these effects, their consumption patterns are a major driver of global biodiversity loss. Land conversion for agriculture, deforestation, overfishing, and water depletion are frequently tied to the demand generated in cities, making Scope 3 a critical, yet often invisible, part of a city's ecological footprint.

Despite its importance, Scope 3 remains the least understood and least measured category of urban biodiversity impact. Methodological complexity, fragmented data, and the global dispersion of environmental pressures make it difficult to trace biodiversity outcomes back to specific urban activities. Traditional accounting systems struggle to connect urban demand with remote ecosystem degradation. However, advances in Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) analysis are opening new opportunities. By linking trade, land use, and ecological impact data, these models allow for an estimation of biodiversity pressures associated with specific commodities. The following case study demonstrates how cities can begin to apply this approach to better understand their global biodiversity footprint and identify points of intervention.

3.3.1 EEMRIO Analysis

To demonstrate the quantification of global biodiversity impacts under Scope 3, we conducted a proof-of-concept analysis using Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) modelling.

Bananas were selected for this modelling exercise based on data availability and methodological suitability. Specifically, the FABIO database—used to support EEMRIO modelling in this deliverable—offers well-integrated and high-resolution data for banana production, trade flows, and land-use characteristics. To ensure complementarity and avoid duplication with ongoing BIOTRAILS modelling work, this analysis was conducted in close collaboration with ETH Zurich. Several coordination meetings were held to refine the approach and ensure that the banana case provided added methodological value while remaining aligned with the overall framework. The banana case study presented here therefore serves as a methodological demonstration, illustrating

how cities could replicate Scope 3 biodiversity assessments for a wide range of commodities, provided the appropriate datasets are available. This value chain exploration also tests the assumption that local food production – regardless of the crop selected – is a sustainable choice.

The Environmentally Extended Multi Regional Input Output (EEMRIO) analysis assessed the environmental footprint of banana consumption in Greece from 1995 to 2020. This method links consumption data to biodiversity pressures in producing regions, enabling cities to trace their global supply chain impacts and identify leverage points for sustainable procurement.

In 2020, Greece consumed 162,444 tonnes of bananas, of which 97.6% were imported. Ecuador alone supplied 88% of all bananas, indicating a high dependency on a single international source. A very small number of the bananas came from local production in Crete, Greece.

Figure 8: Banana Plantation – Vai Beach, Crete. (Source: Dario&Monia [Greece.com](https://www.greece.com))

Local Production

Domestic banana production in Greece is concentrated almost entirely on the island of Crete, primarily in the Arvi-Ierapetra region. Cultivation occurs in both greenhouses and open fields, with greenhouse operations dominating due to Crete's warm, arid climate and irrigation from gorges like Arvi's. Despite their small share in total consumption (2.4%), domestically grown bananas accounted for a disproportionately high share of certain environmental burdens. Annual output is modest—approximately 1,500–3,000 tonnes, covering less than 2% of national consumption. While their environmental footprint for biodiversity and nitrogen is lower, their blue water use remains significant given Crete's water stress. Moreover, drought and economic margins are causing some producers to shift toward more profitable crops such as cucumbers—underscoring the volatility and regional specificity of domestic banana production.

Import vs. Domestic

The biodiversity impact, measured in PDF-year (Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species per year), was almost entirely driven by imported bananas, which contributed 99.95% of the total

biodiversity footprint. This higher percentage (99.95%) compared to the 97.6% import share reflects the significantly greater biodiversity impact per ton of imported bananas—on average, 50 times higher than that of domestically produced bananas. This stark contrast underscores the ecological costs embedded in global food supply chains and the critical role of sourcing decisions in shaping biodiversity outcomes.

This biodiversity footprint, however, does not occur in isolation –other environmental trade-offs emerged across categories. For example, while imported bananas had higher biodiversity and nitrogen application impacts (≈ 4 times higher nitrogen use per ton), domestically produced bananas exhibited a much higher blue water footprint—264 m³ per ton compared to just 55 m³ per ton for imports. These findings illustrate the importance of considering multiple environmental dimensions simultaneously, as reductions in one category (e.g. biodiversity impact) may lead to increases in others (e.g. water use).

It is important to note that the results of this analysis are presented at the national level due to current data availability. However, this methodology is transferable to the city scale, particularly for large metropolitan areas that manage procurement or food distribution systems. With improved access to city-level consumption data, cities could apply the same EEMRIO approach to trace the biodiversity impacts of their own supply chains—strengthening their capacity to make biodiversity-informed procurement decisions and food system interventions. The model could be downscaled to the city level (e.g. Thessaloniki) using per capita GDP as a proxy for consumption, but the analysis still relies on national-level supply chain structures. Downscaling requires clear communication of assumptions, particularly around representativeness and local procurement variation

The study demonstrates that cities can use EEMRIO approaches to quantify Scope 3 biodiversity impacts from specific commodities, enabling data-informed procurement policies. Such analysis provides an evidence base for diversifying sources, setting sustainability standards for imports, and raising awareness of the hidden environmental costs embedded in everyday consumption.

Limitations

While the EEMRIO approach offers a powerful tool for supply chain analysis, it is subject to several limitations. The biodiversity impact factors (PDF-year) are derived from global averages and do not capture local ecological sensitivities or species specific vulnerabilities. Additionally, the FABIO database does not account for temporal variations or regional water scarcity, potentially underestimating the severity of blue water use in water scarce regions like Crete. The FABIO database supports time series analysis, although with some temporal resolution gaps across years. Transport emissions, and retail stage impacts are excluded from the analysis, meaning the results represent a partial but important picture of total supply chain pressures. Despite these constraints, the analysis offers a valuable starting point for cities to identify hotspots and set more biodiversity sensitive procurement strategies.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The application of the three-scope framework in this report demonstrates its practical value for assessing biodiversity impacts at different scales. By considering Scope 1 (within cities), Scope 2 (regional infrastructure), and Scope 3 (global supply chains), the framework provides a structured way to capture the multiple channels through which urban areas influence biodiversity.

The case studies highlight both opportunities and limitations. Urban greening and biodiversity net gain policies (Scope 1) are already supported by clear indicators and governance mechanisms. In contrast, regional infrastructure impacts (Scope 2), such as those linked to Athens' water supply, are less frequently integrated into urban planning despite their ecological importance. Global consumption-driven impacts (Scope 3) remain the least visible, yet the proof-of-concept EEMRIO analysis demonstrates how cities could begin to trace and address these externalised pressures.

Barriers to Implementation and Lessons from Negative Results

The exploration of the three-scope framework across diverse city contexts has also surfaced a range of barriers and limitations—important findings that inform future refinements. Notably, cities reported difficulty accessing reliable biodiversity data, especially for Scope 2 and 3 impacts. In Scope 3, for instance, Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) modelling is theoretically robust—it links global trade flows to environmental pressures using harmonised economic and land-use datasets, allowing for system-wide impact tracing. However, its outputs are typically aggregated at national or regional levels, making it difficult to distinguish between sourcing regions or production methods for a given product. This lack of granularity limits its usefulness for municipal decision-making—for example, a city choosing between different fish species or sourcing origins for procurement would not receive actionable, location-specific biodiversity impact data from EEMRIO results. This can limit its utility for municipal-level decision-making, particularly where cities wish to compare specific procurement choices or design targeted interventions.

Moreover, institutional barriers persist. Environmental departments often lack influence over procurement, infrastructure, or food policy decisions, which are governed by separate departments with different mandates and metrics. In practice, this means that even when biodiversity data is available, it may not be integrated into the decision-making process. Several cities noted that while the framework was conceptually useful, implementation required cross-departmental coordination that is not yet embedded in their institutional cultures.

Finally, cities sometimes struggled to connect abstract biodiversity risks to concrete planning or budgetary decisions. This highlights the need for further development of simple, actionable indicators and for training to accompany the framework's rollout. Addressing these barriers is essential if the framework is to evolve from a promising model into an institutionalised tool for change.

Conclusion

The analysis reveals that cities, despite covering a small fraction of the earth's surface, exert an outsized influence on biodiversity locally, regionally, and globally. Urban green space loss (Scope 1), infrastructure-driven habitat change (Scope 2), and distant land-use changes embedded in supply chains (Scope 3) all contribute to the accelerating biodiversity crisis. Yet these same cities also hold immense potential as incubators of transformative change.

The implementation of the three-scope approach reveals several key insights. First, there is a clear need to strengthen the alignment between local urban actions and global biodiversity targets, ensuring that city efforts contribute meaningfully to broader ecological goals. Second, the approach highlights opportunities to enhance synergies between biodiversity policy and other urban agendas, particularly those focused on climate resilience, circular economy, and public health. Finally, it underscores the importance of involving a wide range of actors—from local communities and municipal departments to producers embedded in global supply chains—in co-creating biodiversity-positive urban pathways.

Ultimately, reversing biodiversity loss demands a reimagining of how we design, govern, and inhabit cities. The findings in this report offer both a caution and a call to action: urban biodiversity must be treated not as a peripheral issue, but as a central pillar of sustainable urban futures.

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